

north american
academic research

Research

Specific structural Interpretation of 3D seismic data in Sijiazhuang Mining area based on Amplitude and Curvature Attribute fusion

**Ehtisham Mehmood¹, Chang Suoliang¹, Muhammad Ali¹, Soban Qamar²*

¹Department of Earthsciences and Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, Shanxi P.R.C

²Institute of Petroleum and Gas Processing, University of Engineering and Technology, Taxila, Pakistan

**Corresponding Author:*

emehmood52@gmail.com

Accepted: 16 september , 2020; Online: 23 september, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4047187>

Abstract: Now, with the rapid development of large-scale mine construction in China, the requirements of three-dimensional seismic exploration and interpretation of coalfields are becoming higher. Numerous new methods are emerging, mainly Attribute technology plays an increasingly important role. Because of the phenomenon that the interpretation accuracy of 3D seismic exploration in coalfield is not high at present, but the seismic exploration accuracy is required to be high due to the high degree of coal mining intensification, we can make full use of attribute interpretation technology and combine the traditional time profile interpretation to identify small structures and we can find some minor faults, collapse columns, and other structural phenomena. This research has been applied in the Sijiazhuang mining area, some small structures have been found, and proper application results have been achieved. It is found that the combination of seismic attribute technology and GeoFrame interpretation system can effectively improve the interpretation accuracy and has high research value.

Keywords: Coalfield 3D Seismic exploration interpretation, seismic attribute technology, small structure, Geo Frame interpretation system.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with the continuous improvement of seismic exploration technology and computer level, 3D seismic data interpretation of the coalfield is also developing rapidly. In the whole process of 3D seismic exploration, there are various new methods, such as seismic coherence technology, inversion technology, attribute technology, and seismic phase analysis technology, which are widely used in multiple related industries (Chen and Wan Zhong 2010). Because of the current situation of 3D seismic data interpretation, the combination of Geo Frame interpretation software and seismic coherence technology, inversion technology, seismic attribute technology, seismic facies analysis technology etc, has effectively improved the interpretation accuracy of small faults and structures. To improve the interpretation accuracy of 3D seismic exploration, with

the gradual development of information technology, coupled with intelligent and visualization technology widely used in the analysis of seismic attributes, there are new methods such as attribute technology. The newly generated attributes have clear geological significance, and the display is more intuitive and clearer, and the interpretation effect is better (Chen Xiao et al., .2005). In China, seismic attribute analysis technology has been developed since the 1980s, mainly used in reservoir description and research. The interpretation of 3D seismic data is based primarily on the manual interpretation of the time section and assisted by attribute interpretation, which results in that 3D seismic data cannot be effectively used, and the interpretation results are challenging to find some small faults and structures. Even false interpretation results such as fake fault phenomena can appear, which reduces the accuracy of interpretation results.

To solve the problems encountered in 3D seismic exploration, make the exploration results more accurate and more in line with the actual production requirements, the development trend of 3D seismic exploration technology is rough as follows (Chen Xiao et al. .2005):

1. Ten thousand channel seismic acquisition technology, single-point excitation, and reception, multi-channel number recording, small area element grid, ultra-high precision 3D seismic acquisition technology with high coverage times.
2. Data processing and mass storage technology (refers to the disk used to store a large amount of data), first develop mass cluster parallel processing technology, at the same time, static correction, pre-stack time migration, and other processing technologies also need to be developed.
3. Excellent seismic data interpretation. With the improvement of computer performance and the continuous development of visual interpretation software, computer group has become the development trend of 3D visual interpretation technology.

Overview and characteristics of the work area

The data of this paper is the 3D seismic data of Shijiazhuang and some useful data. The location of the minefield is southwest high and northeast low, and the loess remains on the top of Taihang Mountain, and the rest of the bedrock is exposed in a large area.

According to the data source borehole statistics in the Shijiazhuang mining area, the 81, 84, and 9 coal seams are all locally recoverable coal seams, and the 15th coal seam is the entire coal seam. The waveform of No. 9 coal seam is unstable and is only an auxiliary; the waveform of No. 15 coal seam is stable and can be continuously tracked, which is the primary basis for this structural interpretation.

Horizon calibration is particularly necessary for 3D seismic data interpretation. It means that the logging data, formation lithology, and seismic reflection waves are related to each other before subsequent horizon tracking, structural analysis and lithological interpretation can be performed.

The geological profile of the Shijiazhuang mining area and the borehole data, synthetic records, and time profiles in the area are compared. The reflection wave T9 wave corresponding to the 9th coal seam in this area and the corresponding wavenumber 15 Reflected wave T15.

2. METHODOLOGY

General process and method of interpretation of three-dimensional seismic data structure in coalfields

Today's three-dimensional seismic exploration is of considerable significance to the development of coal and other resources around the world and is the method with the highest exploration accuracy. However, the interpretation of 3D seismic data mainly based on the manual interpretation of time profile, the auxiliary interpretation of attribute interpretation, resulting in a low utilization rate of 3D seismic data. The interpretation results are challenging to find some small faults and small structures, and even false interpretation results such as fake fault phenomenon, reducing the accuracy of the interpretation results.

In recent years, with the continuous improvement of three-dimensional seismic exploration technology and computer level, the interpretation of three-dimensional seismic data in coalfields is also developing rapidly. Several new methods have emerged in the overall three-dimensional seismic exploration process, such as coherent seismic technology, inversion technology, attribute technology, and seismic phase analysis technology that has been widely used in various related industries. Because of the current situation of three-dimensional seismic data interpretation, the combination of Geo frame interpretation software and seismic coherent technology, inversion technology, seismic attribute technology, seismic phase analysis technology, and other methods can effectively improve the interpretation accuracy of small faults and small structures and enhance the accuracy of interpretation results (Chen Xiao et al. .2005).

2.1 Seismic attribute interpretation method

Seismic attribute interpretation includes attribute extraction, screening, and fusion. Before seismic attribute interpretation, the data needs to be pre-processed to make better use of the application of attribute technology to structural interpretation, improve the accuracy of structural interpretation, and better serve coalfield mining, (Huang et al. 2008).

2.2 Fold and its seismic response characteristics

Fold refers to the bending of underground strata under long-term stress, which has two forms of syncline and anticline (Fu Fangfang 1975) and that are formed in response to motion along fault, diapirism, and regional subsidence or uplift. They are expressed in seismic reflection profiles as one or more regions of dipping reflections that correspond to inclined stratigraphic contacts.

Time section: The reflection wave in-phase axis is uniformly concave as a syncline, and uniformly convex as an anticline.

Horizontal slice: The reflection wave is curved along the same phase axis, the larger the curvature is, the tighter the fold is; the smaller the curvature is, the broader and slower the fold is

Fig. 1: Seismic response of folds in time section

2.3 Fault and its seismic response characteristics

Fault refers to the fracture of underground rock under the action of in-situ stress and the relative displacement along the fracture surface under the effect of force. A large scale is called a fault zone. The hanging wall is above the fracture surface, and the footwall is below the fracture surface. In the two plates of the fault, the hanging wall rises relatively, while the footwall falls relatively to form a reverse fault; the hanging wall falls moderately, and the footwall rises relatively to form a normal fault.

Fig. 2: Seismic response of the fault on the time profile

2.4 Fusion of seismic Attributes

The fusion of different seismic attributes can apply different attribute information at the same time, which helps improve the accuracy of structural interpretation. Human beings rely on the media for communication. (Chen and Wan 2010) Words, sounds, and numbers belong to the media, and especially images are the most direct and clear way. The information contained in the image is much larger than the text information, and its visual effects are strongly influenced by various factors such as color, shape, and form, which have essential value.

With the rapid development of computer technology, computer performance is more powerful, and it is gradually able to better process image information (Chen and Chen Yan 2001). The information that images can reflect is more and more comprehensive, from the original 1-bit black and white mode, 8-bit grayscale mode, to 16-bit high color mode, and 24-bit true-color mode.

Fig. 3: Comparison of three modes of black and white, grayscale, and color

2.5 Extraction and screening of seismic Attributes

To improve the interpretation accuracy of this mining area and identify undiscovered small structures, the characteristics of the 3D seismic data in the study area were extracted. According to the differences in the calculation methods of different attributes, the geological features reflected by the various attributes are different, and the sensitivity to different structures is different (Li Gang et al. 2002). Therefore, this time a total of amplitude-type attributes, frequency-type attributes, curvature-type attributes, coherent attributes, Temporary attributes, and inclination attributes are used for auxiliary explanation.

Before extracting attributes, first, select the appropriate time window. Based on the seismic characteristics of the fault and the significant difference in wave resistance from nearby surrounding rocks, the boundary is clear, its primary frequency is 50Hz, and other characteristics and comprehensive analysis after experimental comparison, the No. 9 and No. 15 coal seams are

used as control horizons, and the Open up and down the time window of 10ms each time to perform attribute extraction,(Li Gang et al. 2002).

Because small faults and deflections in the area are well developed, several attributes that are sensitive to their response will be analyzed during interpretation, including amplitude attributes, curvature attributes, coherence attributes, inclination attributes, and phase attributes. The following is the attribute map extracted during this explanation.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Seismic interpretation based on Amplitude and curvature attribute:

3.1.1 Amplitude attribute:

The amplitude of the stable area is relatively stable. At the same time, the bottom layer around the fault and the subsidence column is discontinuous, the reflected wave energy decays quickly, the reflected wave energy is low, and the amplitude value is low. As shown in Fig.5, the amplitude attribute of 15 number coal is sensitive to the responses of faults and subsidence columns, etc., and it can reflect the position and shape of the structure.

Fig.4: 15 # coal seam Amplitude attribute

3.1.2 Curvature Attribute:

The curvature attribute can highlight small structures such as minor faults and fractures. The curvature analysis can ignore local anomalies and highlight features related to sedimentation and minor errors. As shown in Fig. 6, The curvature property is sensitive to errors and flexure response, and the indication effect is good for 15 number coal.

Fig. 5 15 # coal seam standard deviation maximum positive curvature attribute map

Fig. 6 15 # coal seam instantaneous maximum positive curvature attribute map

3.2 Fusion of seismic attributes

Because the single attribute cannot reflect various structures well, the proposed single attribute is fused to improve the utilization efficiency of the attribute, so that the attribute interpretation technology can better function (Guo Huajun and Liu 2008).

(1) Since the mining area has been mined and the area is relatively large, the southern part of the work area is selected for the extraction and fusion of some attributes, which can be compared with the exposed structures for verification.

(2) As shown in Figure 7, the curvature and amplitude attributes are new attributes generated after RGB attribute fusion. The blue and green parts are normal areas, the red and black shaded parts are abnormal areas, of which the long lines are faults, and the smaller circular ellipses are the positions of sinkholes.

This property has a good effect on fault display, accurate location, and clear form. Its correspondence with the explanation structure is shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 7: 15 # coal seam RGB attribute map phenomenon

Fig .8: 15 # coal seam structural and RGB attribute

(3) Figure 9 shows the new attributes generated by the waveform difference attribute, tilt angle attribute, and instantaneous amplitude attribute after RGB attribute fusion. The shaded area in the figure is the abnormal area, and the rest are normal areas. Among them, the long line is the fault, and the smaller circular ellipse is the position of the sinking column. This attribute has better display effect on faults than single attribute, with accurate location and clear shape.

Fig. 9 15 # coal seam RGB attribute map

4. RESULTS

Using the above-mentioned various attributes and the fused attributes to assist in the interpretation of 3D seismic data, it is found that there are more flexural developments in the whole area, fewer faults in the area, and more developed northern subsidence columns. The overall distribution of tectonic phenomena is reflected in Figure 10. This figure is the structural outline map identified by the 15 # coal seam in this study area.

Fig.10: Structural outline of T15 coal seam

- (1) A total of 12 folds were found in the area this time, and the axial directions were inconsistent. There were mainly two types of north-south and east-west directions. The identification of folds is primarily based on the curvature of the coincident axis in the profile.
- (2) There are a total of 45 faults in the zone, 17 of which have a discontinuity greater than 5m, and 28 of which have a discontinuity of 5m or less. The faults are mostly northwest and northeast. Based on the characteristics of the fault described in the section above, combined with the curvature, inclination, coherence, and variance properties of the fault, which are sensitive to the fault's response, along the coal seam, these faults are shown in the figure below. Use its auxiliary structure to explain. figs 11 and 12.

Fig. 11 Inclination Attribute properties

Fig. 12 Variance Properties

(3) There are a total of 67 sinking columns in the zone, of which 57 are longer than 30m in diameter, and 10 are smaller than or equal to 30m. According to the characteristics of the fault described in the section above, its plane is oval. Combining variance slices, layer slices, coherent slices, and amplitude attributes that are sensitive to the response of the collapse column is shown in the figure below.

Fig.13 Variance Attributes properties

Fig. 14 Amplitude Attributes

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research of related literature, this paper introduces that the full combination of seismic attribute technology and Geo frame interpretation software can effectively improve the interpretation accuracy and has high research value. At present, the accuracy of 3D seismic exploration interpretation of coal fields is not high. Still, due to the high degree of intensive coal mines today, the accuracy of seismic exploration is also high. Using attribute interpretation technology and combining traditional time profile interpretation to identify small structures, we can find some Structural faults such as minor faults and sinking columns. The research findings were applied in the Shijiazhuang mining area, and some small structures were found, which achieved good application results.

It is inevitable to have multiple solutions for 3D seismic interpretation. For this phenomenon, the combination of attribute interpretation technology and time profile is used to improve the accuracy of seismic data interpretation. Still, at the same time, the requirements for raw data will also increase. Meet the needs of "three highs and one standard."

Through comparison, it is found that the properties of curvature, inclination, and coherence slices and variance slices are suitable for fault indication; the amplitude, variance, inclination, energy, and coherence attributes reflect the collapse column better; the variance, inclination, and magnitude attributes deflection Reflective. According to the proposed attributes, the structural interpretation can indicate structural interpretation and improve the accuracy of seismic data interpretation.

Because there are many types of seismic attributes and the geological significance of some attributes is unknown, various attributes can be extracted and filtered based on the characteristics of the target layer and surrounding rocks. Different seismic attributes can be multi-attributed according to different algorithms to generate new attributes. These newly generated attributes can avoid the lack of accuracy in the interpretation of a single attribute, can have clear geological significance, and have a more intuitive and clear display, and a better interpretation effect.

References

- [1] Wang Dawei, Liu Zhen, Chen Xiaohong, et al. Progress of seismic coherence technology and its application in oil and gas exploration [J]. Geological Science and Technology Information, 2005, 24 (2): 71-76.
- [2] Zhang Hongbing, Shang Zuoping, Yang Changchun, et al. Regular parameter estimation of wave impedance inversion [J]. Chinese Journal of Geophysics, 2005, 48 (1): 181-188.
- [3] Marfurt K J, Kirlin R L, Farmer S L, et al. 3-D seismic attributes using a semblance-based coherency algorithm [J]. Geophysics, 1998, 63 (4): 1150.

- [4] Yun Meihou, Ding Wei, Yang Kai. Study on the spatial resolution of seismic traces [J]. Progress in Geophysics, 2005, 20 (3).
- [5] Zhang Jinduo. Status and development trend of seismic interpretation technology [J]. Progress in Geophysics, 2006, 21 (2): 578-587.
- [6] ZHENG Jianjun. Common problems and solutions of geoframe seismic interpretation data management [J]. China Petroleum and Chemical Industry Standards and Quality, 2011, 31 (2): 79-79.
- [7] Qin Jingjing, Li Dechun, Cheng Huihui, et al. Method and application of fine structural interpretation of 3D earthquakes [J]. Energy Technology and Management, 2010 (5): 12-14.
- [8] Chen Tongjun, Cui Ruofei, Lang Yuquan, et al. Interpretation method of 3D seismic fine structure in coal mining area [J]. Progress in Geophysics, 2007, 22 (2).
- [9] Wiederhold H, Bram K, Bunes H A. Glacial structures in northern Germany revealed by a high-resolution reflection seismic survey [J]. Geophysics, 1998, 63 (4): 1265-1272.
- [10] Li Qing. Seismic attribute analysis technology [C] // Jilin Provincial Academic Conference on Science and Technology. 2012.
- [11] Xiong Lei, Zhang Menglu. Study on the characteristics and regularity of geological structure in 3D seismic interpretation of fine exploration [J]. China Petroleum and Chemical Industry Standards and Quality, 2012, 32 (6): 192-192.
- [12] Chen Tongjun, Cui Ruofei, Lang Yuquan, et al. Interpretation method of 3D seismic fine structure in coal mining area [J]. Progress in Geophysics, 2007, 22 (2).
- [13] Wiederhold H, Bram K, Bunes H A. Glacial structures in northern Germany revealed by a high-resolution reflection seismic survey [J]. Geophysics, 1998, 63 (4): 1265-1272.
- [14] Cheng Jianyuan, He Wenxin, Zhu Shujie. Fine interpretation technology of 3D seismic data [J]. Coalfield Geology and Prospecting, 2001, 29 (6).
- [15] Zhao Diandong, Lu Gonghe, Zhang Qinghuai, et al. High-precision 3D seismic acquisition technology and its application effect [J]. Geophysical Prospecting for Petroleum, 2001, 40 (1): 1-8.
- [16] Han Yinfeng. Parallel processing and visualization of massive spatial data in mines based on PC clusters [D]. Northeastern University, 2008.
- [17] Wang Jin. Parallel 3D Prestack Depth Migration Algorithm Based on Microcomputer Cluster [J]. Progress in Exploration Geophysics, 2004, 27 (5): 379-382.
- [18] Guo Huajun, Liu Qingcheng. History, current situation and development trend of seismic attribute technology [J]. Geophysical and Geochemical Exploration, 2008, 32 (1): 19-22.
- 32 (1): 19-22.

- [19] Chen Jun, Chen Yan. Application of seismic attribute analysis in reservoir prediction [J]. Geophysical Prospecting for Petroleum, 2001, 40 (3).
- [20] Tao Wenpeng, Dong Shouhua, Huang Yaping, et al. Application of seismic attribute technology in detecting faults and subsidence columns [J]. Coal Science and Technology, 2008 (12): 83-85.
- [21] Fu Fangfang. "Bright spot" technology-a method to directly search for oil and gas in earthquakes [J]. Petroleum Geophysical Prospecting, 1975, 10 (5): 9-34.
- [22] Zhan Shifan, Wan Zhonghong, Chen Maoshan. Research Progress and Development Direction of New Generation 3D Seismic Attributes [C] // Annual Meeting of Chinese Geophysical Society, Academic Conference of Chinese Seismological Society. 2010.
- [23] Li Gang. Research on seismic thickness prediction method of coal seam thickness and its application [D]. 2012.
- [24] Liu Wenling, Niu Yanliang, Li Gang, et al. Extraction of seismic attributes and validity analysis method for multi-information reservoir prediction [J]. Geophysical Prospecting for Petroleum, 2002, 41 (1).

Acknowledgments

All praises and thanks be to Allah Almighty. Much Appreciation to Taiyuan University of Technology Research Fund Committee for the Research Grant, and to the supervisor for his guidance and recommendations.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

